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Overview of a Scientific Event

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Situations and Leadership in Socio-Cultural Management

On May 10-11, 2023, the 6th annual All-Ukrainian Scientific and Practical Conference “Situational Management and Leadership: Theory, History, Culture and Art of Management” was held at the Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts, organized by the Department of Fashion and Show Business as part of a series of regular professional scientific events in the specialty 028 Management of socio-cultural activities¹.

The scientific event brought together representatives of higher education institutions that train managers of socio-cultural activities: Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts, Kyiv University of Culture, Kremenchuk Mykhailo Ostrohradskyi National University, National Academy of Culture and Arts Managers, Sumy State University, Zhytomyr Applied College of Culture and Arts named after Ivan Ohienko Lviv Vocational College of Culture and Arts and Tulchyn Vocational College of Culture.

The participants of the conference had the opportunity to present scientific developments in various thematic areas: theory and history of situational management; world culture and the art of situational management; leadership

¹ Martynyshyn, Ya. (Head), & Khlystun, O., et al. (Eds.). (2023). *Sytuatsijnyj Menedzhment i Liderstvo: Teoriia, Istoriiia, Kul'tura ta Mystetstvo Upravlinnia [Situational Management and Leadership: Theory, History, Culture and Art of Management]*. Zbirnyk Materialiv VI Vseukrains'koi Naukovo-Praktychnoi Konferentsii Studentiv ta Molodykh Vchenykh [Collection of Materials of the VI All-Ukrainian Scientific and Practical Conference of Students and Young Scientists]. Kyiv: KNUKiM (in Ukr.).

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and social progress; leadership qualities and methods of their development; culture, social adequacy and responsibility of the leader; psychological and pedagogical technologies of formation of charismatic leaders; leadership and the art of situational management in the socio-cultural sphere.

In the presented reports of scientific and pedagogical workers and students of various levels of higher education, a comprehensive theoretical analysis and practical recommendations were presented regarding the organization of situational management and the development of leadership qualities in future managers of socio-cultural activities; such problematic issues as: the theory and history of situational management are considered; world culture and the art of situational management; leadership and social progress; leadership qualities and methods of their development; culture, social adequacy and responsibility of the leader; psychological and pedagogical technologies of formation of leaders; leadership and the art of situational management in the socio-cultural sphere.

The participants of the event raised acute and debatable questions, reflected on the topics of current vectors of development of a modern specialist in the socio-cultural sphere. In particular, professors of the department of fashion and show business of Kyiv National University of Culture and Arts *Ya. Martynyshyn* and *O. Khlystun* emphasized the importance of science and scientific work for universities or any other institutions of higher education, because they cannot exist without achievements in the field of science both on the part of professors and teaching staff and students of higher education. Therefore, one of the most important tasks of quality training of future managers of the socio-cultural sphere is the involvement of student youth in research work, in participation in professional scientific activities, because it is scientific activity that develops the ability to think critically, logically substantiate decisions, and creatively apply the latest achievements of scientific and technical progress in practical activities: “every manager is constantly in the process of solving various problem situations. And his success or failure depends on how much he is able, on the one hand, to “penetrate deeply into the essence of situations, recognize and identify them, be able to notice and understand the invisible, for others, in them (opportunities, threats) and predict their development, and on the other hand, to be able to organize people and act in such a way that the situations in which the manager finds himself develop for the benefit of the organization managed by him and in the desired direction for him”.

The speakers raised the issue of leadership in management taking into account the current political situation in Ukraine, focused attention on the latest approaches to effective management of the organization, on the relevance of the issue of leadership as a social manifestation of personality; (*M. Bryl, V. Opanasiuk, T. Nazarenko, A. Urbanskyi, T. Kovalova*); especially in crisis conditions, the leader's behavior must be supported by a strong professional will, it is in these conditions that the most important functions that a leader must

perform in conditions of uncertainty and instability are: “announcing and jointly accepting the company's vision, defining its directions, developing and evolving the strategy, guaranteeing the compatibility of roles and resources, coaching and creating opportunities, motivating and inspiring employees”.

It is important that situational management is an integral part of the art of management, as it is aimed at flexibility, adaptability and speed of management decision-making, oriented to situations that arise in the internal or external environment of the organization, which in the conditions of today's realities is a guarantee of effective manager activity, and, therefore, the organization (*O. Kalantaievska*), and in general, the situational approach helps quickly and effectively implement management functions under the influence of unpredictable external or internal factors and make management decisions (*O. Krupa*).

Today, there is also a study of the practical implementation of charismatic leadership in modern management (*T. Hryhorchuk, Ye. Kovalenko, Yu. Tymchenko*), because it is precisely such leaders who can effectively act in complex social and political life conditions, be responsible both for their own actions and for the fate of other people, society as a whole, to have a direction for constant self-development and self-projection, to show high resilience and an appropriate level of psychological self-regulation.

The presented scientific research makes it possible to fill the gaps in the professional training of managers of socio-cultural activities: the introduction of situational tasks into the educational process (*T. Povaly*), the formation of the personality of a manager who can set and implement strategic and tactical goals, using the work, talent, and intelligence of different people (*Z. Rybyna*).

Wide interest of the participants of the conference was also aroused by the scientific explorations of higher education students on the problems of the organizational structure of cultural institutions in modern conditions (*M. Burlaka, V. Hryhorchuk, Ye. Zahainova, I. Kazimirov*), their marketing activities (*A. Volia, M. Knysh, A. Lytvynenko, K. Pylypchuk*), branding (*R. Zakharchenko, D. Solonyna*), the relationship between leadership, management and power (*D. Kuzmenko*), the social responsibility of a leader (*I. Lomaka*), the genesis and evolution of production activities (*V. Nikitina*), psychotypes of cultural managers (*O. Sabadin*), etc.

In general, the participants of the conference came to the conclusion that the efficiency and effectiveness of the activities of the organization in the field of culture in unstable conditions, which force all members of the organization to be constantly ready to respond to changes as a result of new circumstances and requests, depend to a large extent on the capabilities of the leader.

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